

AI4

D6.2 Intermediate status report about integration of pilot applications

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

This status report provides an update on the progress made in the integration of pilot applications as part of the AI4EOSC project's Work Package 6 (WP6), identified as Deliverable D6.2. The document outlines the progress, challenges and future directions related to the integration of various pilot applications and provides insights into the collaborative efforts of the consortium partners to achieve the project objectives.

The focal point of this report is on the integration of pilot applications in both internal and external use cases of the project. Each use case is examined in terms of its integration into the platform, combined with a review and update of the respective roadmap to ensure alignment with the project objectives.

In addition, the document addresses the inclusion of examples in the platform as well as feedback from the platform, which includes user perspectives and suggestions for improvement gathered through ongoing interactions. It also highlights the strategies used to effectively engage external users, to promote collaboration, and knowledge sharing within the community.

1. - INTRODUCTION

The AI4EOSC project [\[ai4eosoc\]](#) aims to provide a set of advanced services specifically tailored to the development of Artificial Intelligence (AI), Machine Learning (ML) and Deep Learning (DL) models and applications within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). Multiple components have already been integrated into the platform and are readily available for use cases within the project.

1.1 - SCOPE OF THE DOCUMENT

The deliverable reports on the prototype integration of pilot applications after the first 17 months of the project, describes progress of use cases since the initial collection of requirements and analysis of applications, and updates corresponding roadmaps for the second half of the project.

1.2 - STRUCTURE OF THE DOCUMENT

The document is organised into the following sections:

AI4EOSC platform for users: Provides an overview of the currently accessible components of the AI4EOSC platform from a user point-of-view and highlights upcoming updates designed to enhance the functionality and capabilities of the platform.

Pilot application integration: Each use case of the platform including external early adopters is described in detail, emphasising: a) specifics of integration with the platform b) achieved results and c) a review and update of the roadmap to ensure continuous improvement. AI4EOSC uses the Leading by Example approach to facilitate the integration of pilot applications. The section also describes example applications that have been added to the marketplace and those that are yet to be added.

Platform feedback: This section provides an analysis of the user feedback on the platform, discusses and summarises recommendations from use cases to improve the usability and performance of the platform.

External user engagement: describes strategies and initiatives to foster collaboration with external users.

Conclusion: A concise summary of key findings and insights into the future direction of the AI4EOSC platform.

2. - AI4EOSC PLATFORM FOR USERS

The AI4EOSC platform is an advanced software ecosystem that promotes the development and implementation of Artificial Intelligence, Machine Learning and Deep Learning applications within the European Open Science Cloud (EOSC). It is based on the AI4OS² software stack.

The platform provides users with various components to support them in their developments. In the following, we briefly explain the components that are already integrated into the platform and offered to the user.

2.1 - AVAILABLE COMPONENTS

Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructure (AAI)

The platform leverages the EGI Check-In AAI service [[egi-check-in](#)] to provide federated access to its components. A user must register for the dedicated Virtual Organisation (VO), [vo.ai4eosc.eu](#), in order to use the Training Platform or to self-register for the MLflow tracking service. EGI Check-In is used for Nextcloud storage, AI Project Templates, Inference with OSCAR, and for the Infrastructure Manager.

Storage

The storage is currently managed by the AI4OS Nextcloud instance³, which allows users to store and share data with the current limit of 500GB per user. It

² <https://ai4os.eu/>

³ <https://share.services.ai4os.eu>

is possible to access Nextcloud files from the deployments on the platform in two ways:

- By copying files locally to the deployment hard disk using rclone.
- By mounting the user's Nextcloud directory inside the deployment in the `/storage` path. This is a virtual file system that provides access to Nextcloud storage over the network via the Webdav protocol.

[AI4EOSC Marketplace](#)

The Marketplace⁴ lists all available AI modules and tools with corresponding metadata. This includes tools like Federated learning server, modules developed by various users of the platform, general purpose modules, which can be retrained on user data, and a generic base module, designed as a starting point for creating new deployments (also known as AI4OS Development Environment). This initial perspective is accessible to general (unregistered) users, with limited options. Detailed views for all modules in these sections provide additional information, including a brief description, the module's categories, links to the code repository, the Docker image, and, if available, details about the dataset.

[AI project templates](#)

To simplify the development of new modules and to facilitate integration of an AI model with the DEEPaaS API, a set of software templates based on cookiecutters [[cookiecutter](#)] is provided. The platform offers a web service⁵ to create software projects based on these templates, where three options are available:

- The simple minimal template offers users a minimum of requirements to integrate their code.
- The child module is for users who want to retrain an existing AI module on the marketplace.
- The advanced module, which offers more options on how users can integrate their project

[DEEPaaS API](#)

The DEEPaaS API [[deepaas](#)] is a REST API that leverages the OpenAPI specification and provides the ground to use every module as a part of a more complex service. Through the Swagger interface users can interact with the underlying AI/ML/DL models and instantiate either training of models and doing inference.

[Training platform](#)

Registered users have the option of creating a new deployment, either from scratch or by selecting a module available on the marketplace. Within the general configuration of a deployment, users are required to choose between the Jupyter

⁴ <https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/marketplace>

⁵ <https://templates.cloud.ai4eosc.eu>

or VSC IDE, specify the hardware configuration, provide the Docker tag and optionally provide credentials to mount the Nextcloud user directory. This deployment allows users to develop and train models with the resources available to them. These deployments are accessible by selecting the deployments on the platform.

[Jenkins CI/CD](#)

Jenkins is used to implement CI/CD pipelines (Continuous Integration / Continuous Development) for all software components, including user applications. The pipeline automatically performs a series of actions for users each time users commit a change to their code. This ensures that all information and all builds throughout the project are tested and up to date with users' code.

[MLflow - Experiment Tracking](#)

MLflow [[MLflow](#)] is a platform to streamline ML development, including tracking experiments, packaging code into reproducible runs, and sharing and deploying models. MLflow offers a set of lightweight APIs that can be used with any existing ML application or library (TensorFlow, PyTorch, XGBoost, etc.), wherever (e.g., in jupyter notebooks, standalone applications, or the cloud).

AI4EOSC MLflow deployment is available for users at: <https://mlflow.cloud.ai4eosc.eu>

MLflow Experiments are the primary unit of organisation of runs (a collection of parameters, metrics, tags, and artefacts associated with a machine learning model training process) and used to group the three different use cases.

We analyse and utilise usage statistics for MLflow as seen in [Table 2.1](#) on our platform to continuously enhance its functionalities. This includes the self-registration interface developed to allow users to register into MLflow using their organisation credentials and to share experiments and registered models by granting specific permissions to their team contacts.

MLflow Object/Asset	Details
Experiments(runs) created/logged Metrics logged Params logged	> 15 Experiments created; > 200 (active) Experiment-Runs; > 3000 metrics logged for all runs > 2700 params logged for all runs
Artefacts generated	Models have been generated and stored as artefacts and other objects like (tabular) datasets which consist of 29 GB storage space consumed.
Models stored in Model Registry	More than 15 registered models with different stages like "Production", "Archived" or "Staging" with specific version number.

Total/Average Run Duration(h/m), Minimum Experiment Duration (MiED) Maximum Experiment Duration (MaED)	~ 918 (min)/15 (hours) [counted only finished and active runs] MiED ~ 23 sec MaED ~ 540 min
Signed up Users	15 users

Table 2.1: MLflow objects general summary

Key Elements marked with red arrows are displayed in [Figure 2.1](#).

Figure 2.1: MLflow tracking server - user interface

The advanced information on MLflow specific commands is documented in the platform documentation [[AI4OSdocs](#)]: “How-to’s” -> “Use MLFlow for tracking your trainings” section⁶.

Drift detection

AI/ML/DL models derive their predictive power from historical data, but once deployed in real-world applications, they may face challenges in maintaining accuracy and relevance. The occurrence of concept drift, where the concept previously learned by a model changes, or data drift, where the distribution of incoming data in production deviates from the training data, can lead to biased predictions [[Cespedes2022](#)]. In order to help users identify such types of drifts,

⁶ <https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/user/howto/mlops/mlflow.html>

the AI4EOSC project provides the Frouros⁷ Python package. It is an open-source Python library for drift detection in machine learning systems that allows performing both concept and data drift detection tasks leveraging a variety of implemented detectors.

Inference with OSCAR

The scalable inference of AI models is performed by the AI4OS inference platform, which is based on the open-source serverless platform OSCAR⁸. OSCAR is an open-source platform built on Kubernetes for event-driven data-processing of serverless applications packaged as Docker containers.

The AI4OS inference platform consists of a prepared OSCAR cluster that is exclusively accessible to users belonging to the virtual organisation AI4EOSC (vo.ai4eosc.eu).

Users can access the OSCAR cluster via:

- A web-based user interface⁹ that can be accessed via EGI check-in.
- A command line¹⁰ interface (CLI) that can be accessed via EGI Check-In.

It is also possible to deploy the OSCAR platform on-premises using Infrastructure Manager.

Federated learning server

Federated Learning (FL) [FL] is a widely known approach to distributed training with a focus on privacy, evolving from the traditional centralised approach by distributing the training across multiple clients which collaborate to build a global model. Training an ML or DL model under a federated architecture provides several advantages regarding the classic centralised learning, especially regarding data privacy and security, but also concerning technical requirements and computational resources needed. The classic FL architecture involves a central server and multiple clients, each representing distinct data owners. Clients autonomously train their models locally, avoiding the need to share their private datasets. Model parameters or model updates are securely transmitted to the central server, where they are aggregated according to a predefined strategy or operator, in order to build a global aggregated model. The updated model is then sent back to all the clients, repeating the process during a predetermined number of rounds (until model convergence, ideally). This cyclical process ensures collaborative learning while preserving data privacy.

Various frameworks have emerged in the FL space that facilitate the development and deployment of FL models in various domains. Notable

⁷ <https://frouros.readthedocs.io/>

⁸ <https://oscar.grycap.net/>

⁹ <https://inference.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/>

¹⁰ <https://docs.oscar.grycap.net/oscar-cli/>

examples include TensorFlow Federated (TFF), based on TensorFlow [[TF-Federated](#)] PySyft [[PySyft](#)], which leverages PyTorch; FATE (Federated AI Technology Enabler) [[FATE](#)] hosted by Linux Foundation; NVIDIA Flare [[nvflare](#)]; and Flower [[flower](#)].

Following a comprehensive evaluation of various open source framework options during the project (D3.1¹¹), Flower emerged as the most compelling choice for integration into the AI4EOSC platform due to several key features:

- Ease of use: Flower provides a high-level API that facilitates the implementation of federated learning systems.
- Flexibility with various DL frameworks such as PyTorch and TensorFlow.
- Active community and development.

In this line, the state of the art has also been updated regarding FL tools and frameworks, but also concerning Privacy Preserving Machine Learning (PPML) and other privacy tools to be integrated such as Differential Privacy (DP). In this regard, the objective is to be up-to-date on potential developments in this growing field in order to provide users with the necessary tools for their use cases.

The federated learning server to be used in AI4EOSC has been implemented using Flower and it can be found in the [github repository](#) shown in Figure 2.2.

Figure 2.2: Federated Learning server with Flower. [GitHub repository](#).

This federated learning server, which is integrated as a tool in the AI4EOSC dashboard¹², simplifies the server implementation process: The AI4EOSC platform provides users the possibility to easily start the federated learning server on the platform. This server enables federated training with clients

¹¹ <https://zenodo.org/records/7635430>

¹² <https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/marketplace/tools/deep-oc-federated-server>

deployed on external cloud machines, locally or within the same platform in different deployments. Users can initiate the server effortlessly, facilitating seamless connection with different clients and enabling the start of the training processes. In [Figure 2.3](#) the process of starting the FL server using AI4EOSC is shown. Once started, the clients can connect to the server using the UUID of the FL server deployment.

```
app.py:162 | Starting Flower server, config: ServerConfig(num_rounds=5, round_timeout=None)
app.py:175 | Flower ECE: gRPC server running (5 rounds), SSL is disabled
server.py:89 | Initializing global parameters
server.py:276 | Requesting initial parameters from one random client
server.py:280 | Received initial parameters from one random client
server.py:91 | Evaluating initial parameters
server.py:104 | FL starting
```

Figure 2.3: Federated Learning training within the AI4EOSC platform. Server side.

Currently, work is being carried out to allow client authentication when connecting the different clients with the FL server. We aim to add a deeper privacy layer requiring the clients to introduce a token in order to be able to connect with the FL server, thus trying to prevent poisoning attacks. In addition, Vault¹³ (from HashiCorp) will be used for secret management, integrated with Nomad.

[Infrastructure Manager](#)¹⁴

It is a tool designed to simplify the access and usability of Infrastructure as a Service (IaaS) clouds for scientific applications. It automates the selection, deployment, configuration, monitoring, and update of virtual appliances. It supports APIs from various cloud platforms, provides a contextualisation system for installing and configuring user-required applications, and offers multiple access methods, including a web-based GUI, an XML-RPC API, a REST API, and a command-line application.

[AI4OS Documentation](#)

¹⁵

AI4OS is the name of the generic software stack that is powering the deployments of different platforms such as AI4EOSC or iMagine. The documentation for using this software and corresponding platform is detailed in [\[AI4OSdocs\]](#). It includes a quickstart together with further explanations on how to train or develop a model or how to use the provided tools. In addition, it provides users with an overview concerning the platform, the dashboard, the authentication, data storage resources, the inference platform (OSCAR), MLflow tracking server, etc.

¹³ <https://www.vaultproject.io/>

¹⁴ <https://im.egi.eu/im-dashboard/login>

¹⁵ <https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/>

User Support

The use cases of the AI4EOSC project are supported in various ways.

The AI4EOSC project has set up dedicated email lists to facilitate communication and support within the community. Users are encouraged to subscribe to the email lists to seek assistance, share experiences, and stay informed about the latest developments.

Jira¹⁶ issue tracking facilitates the reporting and resolution of issues. Users can use the Jira system to report and log issues, report bugs, and request new features.

In addition, bi-weekly remote conferencing is organised to facilitate direct communication between the use cases of the platform and the developers.

External users get support via the ai4eosc-support@listas.csic.es email channel and dedicated remote conferences if necessary.

2.2 - PLANNED UPDATES

The second release of AI4EOSC is making steady progress with a focus on adding new functionalities to the already available components and including new components and tools. The development of AI4Compose¹⁷, which involves integrating Elyra¹⁸, Node-RED¹⁹, and deploying FlowFuse²⁰, is currently on the way. Significant efforts have begun to enable model and data versioning by utilising the MLflow tool [MLflow]. In the pipeline are plans to provide experiment-centric dashboard tools, and streamline inference deployments to OSCAR. As a part of the ongoing efforts, we are actively working on drift monitoring and detection tools, with Frouros Python package already being implemented, and on establishing AI model provenance tools for providing semantic information about AI models and datasets, training and inference processes. In addition, more tools for distributed machine learning with a focus on privacy preservation are planned to be released in AI4EOSC 2.

3. - INTEGRATION OF PILOT APPLICATIONS

The section describes the implementation of user applications in accordance with the plan developed in D6.1 and shown in [Figure 3.1](#). Two software releases of user applications are planned: by M16 (December 2023) and by M32 (April 2025) of the project. Following the roadmap, all use cases published their

¹⁶ <https://jira.ifca.es/secure/Dashboard.jspa>

¹⁷ <https://github.com/ai4os/ai4-compose>

¹⁸ <https://github.com/elyra-ai>

¹⁹ <https://nodered.org/>

²⁰ <https://forge.flows.dev.ai4eosc.eu/>

minimum viable products (MVP) in December 2023 and entered the second iteration of AI application development.

Figure 3.1: Application development and release plan for pilot applications

3.1 - UC1-AGROMETEOROLOGY

Anthropogenic-driven climate change is expected to affect, mainly to increase, frequency and intensity of various types of extreme events. One of them are thunderstorms that generate adverse phenomena for farmers:

- high winds can break and damage buildings, equipment, material and plants;
- hail can cause leaf damage reducing yield or destroying plants, machines, cars, and buildings;
- flash floods can endanger humans, animals, damage machines and equipment, can lead to loss of topsoil as well as damage to crops.

In this use case we process radar imagery - utilising AI ensemble stacking and federated learning - to create added value products for improving farmers activity, namely timely and precise warnings of thunderstorms for farmers. As an enhancement, the farmer wants to know when exactly thunderstorms will hit his area so that he can get everyone to safety. Nowcasting can provide localised warnings around 30 minutes ahead of thunderstorms. We integrated the use case with the platform, which enabled us to use existing AI model templates and state-of-the-art computing resources, perform automated testing and use other platform tools to tackle the problem. The model is a neural network currently, where the number of layers can be set by the user.

Enhancements:

- Configurable AI architecture thanks to the AI4EOSC platform.
- Use of radar data distributed into several federated clients (artificial split in different non-overlapping zones) for performing a FL training adapted to each zone. The goal is to analyse the performance of this approach in the case of radar data distributed in different areas, in order to promote collaboration between organisations having this kind of data. An example of the preliminary results of this approach can be seen in [Figure UC1.1](#), showing three predictions obtained for one of the areas analysed using the FL architecture. All the code for training that global model and getting the predictions and the visualisation has been developed within the AI4EOSC platform. This work is still under development and is under active preparation for potential publication.

For this use case the use of the federated learning approach can be interesting due to different reasons (other than privacy, which do not really apply to radar data):

- First, to enhance collaboration since in some cases the access to these data is not open (i.e. they are expensive) but it could be studied to use them in a collaborative way to build robust models (collaboration between institutions handling such data without sharing it).
- Radar data generally have a distributed nature (depending on the area where they have been taken), so it is interesting to analyse if training models in a federated way gives better results than training with individual data from each radar/area. It may not be possible to centralise in the same place for technical/storage/computational cost reasons.

Figure UC1.1: Example of predictions of the test set of radar data using Federated Learning.

In the second half of the project, we plan to enrich the ensemble stacking with in-situ measurements and numerical weather predictions (NWP) outputs, which add richer meteorological information to the model.

3.1.1 - Integration with the platform

Integrated components

Component	Description of Utilisation
Storage (Nextcloud)	We store a large amount of input radar data on the Storage. NextCloud is an inevitable storage area, as the virtual machines have limited space available. We use GUI access for small data transfers and setting sharing for partners in the project and <code>rclone</code> for large data transfers. Firstly used https://data-deep.a.incd.pt/ and newly https://share.services.ai4os.eu/ .
AI4EOSC Marketplace	Marketplace is used as inspiration for projects. Our model is published on the marketplace to support dissemination and exploitation.
AI projects from templates	We used the cookiecutter template with minor changes to set up initial repository structures. It helped us to integrate the model code with the platform simpler.
DEEPaaS API	We integrated our project "Thunderstorm nowcast for agrometeorology" with DEEPaaS API. We developed the following endpoints: <code>get_metadata</code> , <code>get_predict_args</code> , <code>predict</code> , <code>get_train_args</code> , <code>train</code> . We configured that data can be uploaded as a file or URL (NextCloud). Users can define the neural network architecture training

	by yaml file.
Training platform	The MVP has been trained on basic neural networks. We have to improve the training process in the next steps.
MLflow	Not yet used. We are in the phase of studying documentation.
Jenkins CI/CD	We used Jenkins for CI/CD purposes relating to the process of publishing to the Marketplace. Jenkins permits us to automatise diverse aspects of software development.
Federated Learning server	Several tests are being carried out to analyse the feasibility of the FL architecture applied to artificially distributed radar data in different areas. An analysis of the predictions obtained and a comparison with classical approaches has been performed in order to study whether a greater generalisation ability of the models is obtained.
AI4OS Documentation	Used extensively: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • During onboarding. • When learning each new feature of the platform. • Consulted during the whole project.
User Support	User Support contacted: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • When no access to Nextcloud.

Table UC1.1: Summary of UC1-Integrated Components

Achieved results

- The MVP (Minimum Viable Product) is defined
- Coding status
 - DEEPaaS API for input data is added
 - Coding is finished for minimal viable version - Progress 100%
- Unit tests are running
- MVP is published on the Marketplace ²¹

The AI training can be run from the Marketplace. The user can upload data to the NextCloud and start training and experimenting with different configurations of hyperparameters and model architecture.

According to the tests performed until now for predicting the water content in the atmosphere, the federated learning approach with an adaptive phase (training the global FL model a few epochs in each zone after finishing) slightly improves the results in comparison to non-federated approaches. Specifically, we have analysed the use of this kind of federated architecture together with the adaptive

²¹ https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/marketplace/modules/uc-microstep-mis-deep-oc-ai4eosc_thunder_nowcast_ml

phase in comparison to the predictions given by the classic *Continuity Tracking Radar Echoes by Correlation* (COTREC) model, which was used for this purpose. We have noted that the FL approach presents greater generalisation capacity in the context of unseen data.

3.1.2 - Review and update of the roadmap

Applying the methodology of the application analysis defined in D6.1, the following Epics were identified:

- Epic 1 (E01): Productive data science
- Epic 2 (E02): Extensible and integrable forecasting product

The User stories²² for every Epic are listed in [Figure UC1.2](#) with the corresponding implementation timelines.

Figure UC1.2: UC1 user stories and the development roadmap

Planned improvements

Experiments will be performed with various AI techniques to select the one with best results. The following functions of the platform will be integrated:

- MLFlow will be used in the next steps for experiments tracking.
- DVC will be used for data versions tracking.

²² User stories are cited as Ex.USy, which stands for User story Y within Epic X

- Frouros is planned to be used for detecting possible input radar data quality drifts, i.e. for monitoring model in production.

Towards the end of the project, inference via OSCAR platform will be considered. Additionally, the model outputs will be interfaced (via DEEPaaS API) to external forecasting system capable of notifying end users. Also, the in-situ measurements and numerical weather predictions (NWP) outputs will be added to the ensemble stacking, to achieve better results when using this additional meteorological information.

3.2 - UC2-PLANT PROTECTION

The use case about plant protection aims to determine the risk of disease in agricultural crops and determine the phases of plant growth and the condition of crops. The developed AI models are going to be integrated into existing national advisory platforms, operated by WODR²³ (Wielkopolska Agricultural Advisory Centre in Poznań) and PSNC.

WODR and PSNC are currently operating a national advisory platform for farmers (eDWIN²⁴), which includes a network of meteorological ground stations, the Farm Management System, and ground observations of the occurrence of diseases and pests. The current solutions are based on predictive mathematical models.

The plan is to add to the current mathematical prediction ML/DL-based models used for early detection of the plant diseases and add new sources of the data.

The specialists in the field used the tool LabelStudio to mark the areas of the leaf covered by the disease symptoms. It helped to create masks that were used in the training of the model (see [Figure UC2.1](#)).

²³ <https://www.wodr.poznan.pl/>

²⁴ <https://www.edwin.gov.pl/>

Figure UC2.1: top image: Marked leaf area; middle: Leaf separated from the whole plant; bottom: Mask as a result.

3.2.1 - Integration with the platform

Integrated components

Component	Description of Utilisation
Storage (Nextcloud)	Firstly we use https://data-deep.a.incd.pt/ and next we move to https://share.services.ai4os.eu . We use nextcloud to store and host our four models which users download during creating deployments of Integrated Plant Protection on Marketplace. Then users can use these models for inferencing or as pretrained models. We also use Nextcloud as main storage for our datasets. We gather data from eDWIN or from our partners and send it to Nextcloud. In the next step, we use part of this data as datasets in Label Studio. We configure Label Studio with Nextcloud so that the data automatically moves to nextcloud after labelling. Thanks to this, we have fully synchronised datasets. We store almost 8 GB of images. In the next step we use these datasets in training.
AI4EOSC Marketplace	We publish our MVP on the Marketplace. Before the process of creating our module, we actively used and tested modules such as "Train image classifier" and "2D semantic segmentation". When we created our module in "AI4OS Development Environment"
AI projects from templates	We used AI projects from templates to create test projects for developing test apps according Documentation. In the next step we created a template for our module. We configured github repositories which were required to connect with AI4EOSC.
DEEPaaS API	We integrated "Integrated Plant Protection" with DEEPaaS API. The following endpoints were developed: <code>get_metadata</code> , <code>warm</code> , <code>get_predict_args</code> , <code>predict</code> , <code>get_train_args</code> , <code>train</code> . We configure that data can be uploaded as a file or URL. Users can define training parameters and additionally may choose to apply pre-processing.
Training platform	Used during the whole process of projecting and creating an MVP we use the Training platform. We created test deployments of modules available on the marketplace to check how our data will be classified with these modules. In the next step we use a training platform in the process of developing and testing Integrated Plant Protection.
MLflow	Model versions stored: in the progress Custom loggings: datasets for instance Compare experiments through charts Model sharing: no

Jenkins CI/CD	We used Jenkins for CI/CD purposes. Jenkins allows us to automate various aspects of the software development lifecycle, including building, testing.
AI4OS Documentation	In the whole process on WP6 we used the AI4OS Documentation.
User Support	We contacted User Support when we had technical problems like difficulties of logging in Nextcloud.

Table UC2.1: Summary of UC2-Integrated Components

Achieved results

- Minimum Viable Product²⁵ is published on the marketplace and ready to use.
- Four models were prepared (two for rye and two for beet) to determine whether a plant is covered by a disease.
- Six sets of beet and rye (three per plant) photos were used as a source.
- The coding phase is finished and DEEPaaS API is integrated.
- Unit tests were performed and they raised no issues.
- Tensorboard and Mlflow are also added.

3.2.2 - Review and update of the roadmap

This use case follows the requirements described by user stories. Stories concerning direct platform usage were given the highest priority. Primary objectives were obtained by intensively utilising available platform resources and integrated components. This use case faced the most difficulties with data availability (considerably low amount of photos), data quality, and inference logic adaptation for best-achieving results. Delayed tasks concern tools designed for continuous dataset monitoring. Adaptation of the data acquisition toolchain in the working system gives opportunities for stable updates only in the low season of usage.

²⁵ https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/marketplace/modules/uc-ai4eosc-psnc-deep-oc-integrated_plant_protection

Figure UC2.2: UC2 user stories and the development roadmap

Planned improvements

In the second half of the project the following aspects will be considered for use case evaluation and progressive development:

- Use of synthetic data: Incorporating synthetic data into the dataset to augment and enhance the existing training data for machine learning models.
- Deploying more mature MVP on Marketplace: Introducing a more refined Minimum Viable Product (MVP) to the marketplace, accompanied by supporting tools to enhance its functionality and usability.
- Integration of MLflow and CVAT tools: Implementing MLflow, a machine learning lifecycle management platform, alongside CVAT tools for image

annotation. This integration can streamline the development and deployment of computer vision models.

- Inference architecture evaluation: Evaluating and potentially upgrading the architecture used for model inference, which is crucial for ensuring efficient and accurate predictions in production environments.
- Utilisation of gradio with model metadata: Leveraging Gradio along with model metadata to improve the showcasing of results. Gradio can be used for building interactive demonstrations or interfaces for machine learning models, and incorporating model metadata can enhance transparency and understanding of model behaviour.

3.3 - UC3-AUTOMATED THERMOGRAPHY

Use case 3 leverages thermal UAV-based imaging and AI to identify “hot spots” (thermal anomalies) in urban settings and thus improve the efficiency of energy-related systems. The two scenarios being examined are

- I. Detecting thermal hotspots on building rooftops caused by thermal bridges to support urban planners and building owners with retrofitting plans.
- II. Detecting thermal hotspots caused by common urban features (cars, manholes, streetlamps, etc.) to aid district heating network operators in their search for pipeline leakages by automatically removing these false alarms from the list of potential suspects (see [Figure UC3.1](#)).

A current inability to quickly and accurately pinpoint areas of unwanted heat loss leads to a drop in energy efficiency. The overarching objective therefore lies in automating the detection of such thermographic anomalies to accelerate the implementation of necessary counter-measures and repairs.

AI can be used to this end as either a stand-alone tool (I) or through integration into a pre-existing analysis pipeline (II).

Figure UC3.1: Example of thermal urban feature segmentation (I), including the input data of combined RGB (top left) and TIR (top right) images, the manually annotated segmentation mask (bottom left), and the prediction made by the trained U-Net model (bottom right).

3.3.1 - Integration with the platform

Integrated components

Component	Description of Utilisation
Storage (Nextcloud)	Nextcloud is actively used for storage purposes of the required datasets, a default model for inference, and any models trained on the platform for both I.) and II.). The new feature of accessing the storage space directly from within the deployment instead of via <i>rclone</i> simplifies data transfer and usage greatly. Most recently, all data has been moved to the new Nextcloud instance at https://share.services.ai4os.eu/ .
AI4EOOSC Marketplace	The marketplace, with its store of published modules, is used as a point of reference and several examples were inspected to aid in designing the use case modules. Scenario I has now been added to the marketplace itself.

AI projects from templates	The cookiecutter template(s) helped set up initial repository structures and thus simplify integrating model code with the platform. For scenario I.), the standard master template was used, while scenario II.) API repository is based on the new, advanced template.
DEEPaaS API	Owing to the use of the cookiecutter templates, both scenarios are designed to be integrated with the DEEPaaS API, connecting to the endpoints <code>get_metadata</code> , <code>get_predict_args</code> , <code>predict</code> , <code>get_train_args</code> , and <code>train</code> .
Training platform	Each scenario has its deployment with a Tesla T4 GPU. The docker base images vary according to the requirements of the implemented model toolboxes - MMDetection for I.), which requires PyTorch; segmentation_models for II.), which uses tensorflow.
MLflow	MLFlow has been integrated for experiment tracking in scenario II.). As the utilised segmentation_models toolbox offers only few metrics, an additional evaluation script calculates common metrics for semantic segmentation, including accuracy, balanced accuracy, IoU, weighted IoU, F1, precision, and weighted precision, as well as class-wise evaluations of these due to the skewed nature of the multi-class dataset. 45 metrics are set up in total to be recorded in MLFlow, allowing for a comparison of various experiment runs.
Jenkins CI/CD	Scenario I.) currently actively uses Jenkins for Continuous Integration (CI) and Continuous Delivery (CD). It allows the automation of various parts of the software development lifecycle and is part of the process of publishing to the Marketplace.
AI4OS Documentation	The documentation serves as a guideline and starting point in understanding platform functionalities and can aid in solving common issues. It is used continuously throughout the project.
User Support	In matters that go beyond the docs, user support is very helpful in quickly and efficiently providing aid for problem solving. It has been and is made use of continuously throughout the duration of the project.

Table UC3.1: Summary of UC3-Integrated Components

[Achieved results](#)

- I. “Thermal Bridges on Building Rooftops” Detection (TBBDet):
 - The AI object detection model is implemented
 - DEEPaaS API coding for minimal viable version is functional
 - Unit tests started

- Module (Model + API) is published²⁶ on the Marketplace for the detection of thermal bridges on building rooftops in combined thermal and RGB image data
- II. “Thermal Urban Feature” Segmentation (TUFSeg):
- The AI semantic segmentation model is defined with multiple data preprocessing options to select from
 - DEEPaaS API coding for minimal viable version is functional
 - MLFlow is integrated for experiment tracking

3.3.2 - Review and update of the roadmap

Using the previously developed user stories and epics as guidance, the use case focused on developing AI models and integrating them with the platform in the form of minimum viable products. This was achieved for the existing TBBRDet model and developed TUFSeg model, both of which are or are close to being published to the Marketplace. Implementing this for two separate scenarios was quite ambitious and, owing to unforeseen challenges (for example in resource allocation or setting up dependencies), code testing is somewhat behind schedule and will be a key aim for the next months. By contrast, experiment tracking is well underway for TUFSeg via MLFlow.

[Figure UC3.2](#) shows the current status of the user stories and epics roadmap.

Planned improvements

For the second half of the project, the use case plans to focus on utilising other features the platform has to offer, such as for instance federated learning. This approach can provide some advantages when working with images captured in different cities and would facilitate the collaboration among different network operators. An additional asset would be a form of interface for not only inference but also training, as this would allow for the conduction of diverse architecture and data preprocessing ablation studies to identify the best model variant. A comprehensive inference GUI could additionally allow for an integrated active learning loop, where users would judge model predictions to provide new annotation data.

²⁶ https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/marketplace/modules/uc-envollmer-deep-oc-tbbrdet_api

Figure UC3.2: UC3 user stories and the development roadmap

3.4 - APPLICATIONS OF THE LEADING BY EXAMPLE APPROACH

The "leading by example" approach refers to the practice of demonstrating desired behaviours or solutions through concrete examples or implementations. Within the AI4EOSC project, providing example applications of AI models with additional APIs serves several important purposes:

- **Guidance:** By showing concrete implementations, we demystify the process of adding deep APIs to AI code and provide practical insights.
- **Acceleration:** By providing ready-to-use examples, we accelerate the development process for use cases. Developers can use these examples as a foundation, saving time and effort in creating similar functionality from scratch.
- **Quality assurance:** Our examples serve as a benchmark for quality and consistency.
- **Ready-to-use Docker images for general purpose models:** The examples primarily consist of general purpose models. Use cases can download the

ready-to-use Docker images of these models and train the model on their own dataset without any effort in coding the AI model.

3.4.1 - Example applications

The CNN model is well suited for object detection, and current object detection algorithms can be divided into two main categories: two-stage detectors, such as RCNN [[rcnn](#)], Fast-RCNN [[fast-rcnn](#)], and Faster-RCNN [[frcnn](#)], and one-stage detectors, such as You Only Look Once (YOLO) [[yolo](#)].

When considering AI models for image processing, the choice between Faster R-CNN and YOLO depends on specific requirements, including computing resources, accuracy, and real-time processing needs. [Table LE.1](#) is a brief comparison to help you decide:

Metric	DL Application		Dataset	Suitability
	Faster R-CNN (VGG)	YOLO (VGG)		
Accuracy (mAp)	73.2	7	PASCAL VOC 2007+2012	Well suited for tasks where high accuracy is required. Suitable for scenarios where real-time processing is not a strict requirement.
Speed(FPS)	66.4	21	PASCAL VOC 2007+2012	Ideal for applications that require real-time processing, Suitable for tasks where slightly lower accuracy is acceptable in exchange for faster inference.

Table LE.1: Comparison of the performance and speed of Faster RCNN and YOLO. The results are from [[yolo](#)]

In recent years, the YOLO model has evolved considerably with the development of new versions designed to improve both the accuracy and efficiency of the system. YOLOv8 [[yolov8](#)] is the latest version of the YOLO model, which has significantly improved both the speed and accuracy of object detection. This model introduces various variants, including nano (n), small (s), medium (m), large (l), and xlarge (x) with a different number of variables that can be trained depending on the model variant. [Figure LE.1](#) illustrates the performance in terms of mean Average Precision (mAP) versus the number of parameters and latency across different versions and variants of the YOLO model.

Figure LE.1: The plot on the left shows the performance in terms of mAP vs the number of parameters and the right-hand side shows the latency vs the performance in terms of mAP of the different versions and variants of the Yolo model²⁷

The external repository [fasterrcnn-pytorch-training-pipeline](https://github.com/sovits-123/fasterrcnn-pytorch-training-pipeline)²⁸ provides a pipeline for training PyTorch FasterRCNN models on custom datasets. With this pipeline, users have the flexibility to choose between official PyTorch models trained on the COCO dataset, use any backbone from Torchvision classification models, or even define their own custom backbones. The trained models can be used for object detection tasks on the specific datasets. We have integrated the DEEPaaS API into this existing codebase and this model is accessible as a general-purpose model on the marketplace²⁹.

The Ultralytics community [[ultralytics](https://ultralytics.com)] is an active contributor to the open source community, providing accessible and cutting-edge solutions for various artificial intelligence tasks such as detection, segmentation, classification, tracking, and pose estimation. YOLOv8 [[ultralytics_yolov8](https://ultralytics.com/yolov8)] is provided by the Ultralytics organisation using the Pytorch framework. This model can be used flexibly for classification, detection, oriented object detection, and segmentation tasks. We have integrated a DEEPaaS API into the Ultralytics YOLOv8 and make it available as a general-purpose model on the marketplace³⁰. As we can see in [Figure LE.1](#), there is a trade-off between the accuracy and latency of the model. Depending on the application, users can select one of the model variants and train it.

The Docker images are provided together with these models. The users have the option of either starting a deployment on the dashboard from this Docker image and training the models on the custom data without further effort or running these Docker containers on both Clouds and High-Performance Computing

²⁷ Figure was copied from <https://docs.ultralytics.com/models/rtdetr/#overview>

²⁸ <https://github.com/sovits-123/fasterrcnn-pytorch-training-pipeline>

²⁹ https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/marketplace/modules/deep-oc-fasterrcnn_pytorch_api

³⁰ https://dashboard.cloud.ai4eosc.eu/marketplace/modules/deep-oc-yolov8_api

(HPC) infrastructures. In the latter case, users can leverage udocker container tool [[udocker](#)].

In the 'test' branch of the Faster R-CNN repository³¹ and the 'mlflow' branch of the YOLOv8 repository³², MLflow integration has been incorporated into the code. This addition empowers users with the capability to track and monitor the progress of their experiments during training.

3.4.2 - Planned additions

Segment Anything model (SAM) [[seg-anything](#)] is a breakthrough model for image segmentation that improves both the speed and quality of computer vision annotations. One of the most compelling features of SAM is its ability as a promotable segmentation system, demonstrating zero-shot generalisation to unfamiliar objects and images, eliminating the necessity for additional training. Zero-shot learning [[zero-shot](#)] is a machine learning paradigm in which a model is trained to recognise classes or objects that it has never seen during the training phase by adding some form of additional information or knowledge about these unseen classes, enabling the model to generalise and make predictions even for unfamiliar instances. SAM uses zero-shot learning to segment unseen objects during inference. SAM can be asked to:

- perform edge detection, segment anything, including object proposal generation.
- segment detected objects, essentially performing instance segmentation.
- as a proof-of-concept, to segment objects from free-form text.

SAM is available under a permissive open licence (Apache 2.0)³³. We are investigating adding the fine-tuning of the SAM to the marketplace.

The research study [[RNA](#)] provides a thorough investigation of the challenges and prospects associated with training deep learning models in scientific domains, with a focus on molecular biosciences. The authors emphasise the lack of annotated data, especially with respect to RNA, despite its central role in the "dark matter" of the genome, and advocate the use of self-supervised learning techniques as a promising solution to mitigate the lack of high-quality data in RNA research. In particular, the study highlights contributions to the prediction of RNA contact prediction, such as the improvement of downstream decision tree models. We intend to include this model as an example in the platform. The pre-trained checkpoint provided by the authors facilitates the prediction of RNA contact maps, and it is planned to make the fine-tuning of downstream models available. Fine-tuning is the process of adapting a pre-trained model to a specific

³¹ https://github.com/deephdc/fasterrcnn_pytorch_api/tree/test

³² https://codebase.helmholtz.cloud/m-team/ai/yolov8_api/-/tree/mlflow?ref_type=heads

³³ <https://github.com/facebookresearch/segment-anything>

task or domain by further training it with task-specific data. This will allow scientists in biosciences to customise the model using their own datasets, increasing its utility in different research contexts.

Large Language Models (LLM) represent a groundbreaking advance in natural language processing (NLP) technology. These models, such as OpenAI's GPT [\[GPT\]](#) series and Google's BERT [\[BERT\]](#), have demonstrated remarkable capabilities in understanding and generating human-like text for a variety of tasks. The use of LLMs for various applications has become increasingly common due to their adaptability and effectiveness.

In line with the advances in LLMs, we are considering integrating the fine-tuning capabilities of some LLM into the AI4EOSC marketplace.

3.5 - EARLY ADOPTERS FROM EXTERNAL USERS

Apart from the internal use cases, there are also early adopters of the platform from either a consortium participant institute or who reached the project via the EOSC Digital Innovation Hub (DIH)³⁴ or via the EGI ACE³⁵ project.

It is important to note that the software stack AI4OS being developed in this AI4EOSC project, is also used to build the iImagine AI platform of the iImagine³⁶ project with further 8 use cases in aquatic science. The progress of iImagine use cases is reported in the iImagine deliverable D3.2 [\[iImagine-D3.2\]](#).

3.5.1 Waste Management in Construction Sites

Effective waste management in construction sites necessitates precise identification and location of various materials. Traditional methods can be time-consuming and often inaccurate. Through the use of DIH cloud resources such as GPUs, CPUs, RAM, and disk space, we were able to train and evaluate a state-of-the-art Deep Learning model capable of effectively identifying and segmenting objects of our interests appearing in construction sites, such as wooden pallets, bricks, scaffoldings, etc.

Specifically, we have leveraged the unprecedented capabilities in object detection and segmentation of the YOLOv7³⁷ model by fine-tuning the larger pre-trained model which consists of 37 million trainable parameters. Through the use of the provided resources, we were able to train and compare different methods with different model sizes, concluding that YOLOv7 yields the highest performance.

³⁴ <https://eosc-dih.eu/>

³⁵ <https://www.egi.eu/project/egi-ace/>

³⁶ <https://www.imagine-ai.eu/>

³⁷ <https://github.com/WongKinYiu/yolov7>

Integrated components

Component	Description of Utilisation
Training platform	We have requested and used up to 3 virtual machines equipped with NVIDIA's Tesla T4 and Tesla V100-PCIE-32GB GPU.
AI4OS Documentation	Utilised in order to understand what is the most convenient way to use the training platform as well as how to get access to the virtual machines and how to set up them. The provided guidelines are very helpful and informative.

Table EA1.1: Summary of Integrated Components utilised in "Waste Management in Construction Sites" use case.

Achieved results

After conducting several experiments tuning the hyperparameters of models with various architectures, we ended up with a fine-tuned YOLOv7 model achieving 64.51% mean Average Precision (mAP) over bounding boxes and 51.87% mAP over masks, averaged over the 4 classes (object types) of our interests.

The [Table EA1.2](#) below presents the most indicative results obtained during our experiments. We have compared YOLOv7 with YOLOv8³⁸ model, since YOLOv8 provides several pretrained models of different sizes. We have concluded that YOLOv7 yields the best results but with small differences compared to YOLOv8m-seg.

Metric	DL Application			Dataset
	YOLOv7	YOLOv8m-seg	YOLOv8x-seg	
Bbox-mAP(0.5)	64.51%	64.08%	61.48%	Custom
Mask-mAP(0.5)	51.87%	51.85%	51.89%	

Table EA1.2: Comparison of the performance YOLOv7 and YOLOv8 using our own custom dataset. The results reported are computed based on our validation set.

[Figure EA1.1](#) provides some detection and segmentation examples of wooden pallets acquired using our fine-tuned YOLOv7 model. Due to privacy concerns, we

³⁸ <https://github.com/ultralytics/ultralytics>

cannot provide images from real construction sites, thus we present results obtained using synthetic data created by NVIDIA's omniverse³⁹ tool.

Figure EA1.1: Wooden pallet detection and segmentation examples obtained by applying our fine-tuned YOLOv7 model on synthetic data.

Planned improvements

In the future, we are going to collect more data augmenting our custom dataset, since the quantity (along with the quality) of the dataset plays a significant role in the training of large Deep Learning models. Additionally, we have planned to design and implement a novel tracking method which will work in conjunction with our YOLOv7 model. In this way, we will be able not only to detect and segment objects of our interest but also to count them, which is a crucial process in applying AI (Deep Learning) in the domain of “Waste Management in Construction Sites”.

³⁹ <https://www.nvidia.com/en-eu/omniverse/>

3.5.2 DigitalAlimenta

DigitalAlimenta [[DigitalAlimenta](#)] is a project of the Spanish National Research Council (CSIC) that aims to provide a tool to improve the quality of food and facilitate food studies for researchers in this field. A fundamental part of this tool is to obtain precise measurements of certain foods. Currently, we are focusing on fruits to obtain reliable results in dietary studies. To do this, we are developing a deep learning tool that predicts the weight of certain fruit from a single view image.

Thanks to the AI4EOSC platform, we have been able to use the necessary computational resources, such as GPUs, CPUs, RAM and disk space, to train and evaluate a model capable of predicting the weight of apples with an acceptable margin of error. This platform has allowed us to create a neural network and implement several common deep learning techniques, such as transfer learning, data-augmentation, bootstrapping and cross-validation.

Integrated components

Component	Description of Utilisation
Training platform	We have requested and used one virtual machine equipped with a GPU. This is a key component for developing the model due to its complexity.
Storage (Nextcloud)	The AI4EOSC nextcloud instance has been used for storing and reading the data used for training and validating the model. Our dataset requires 40 GB of disk space so this is a quite important component for our use case.
AI4OS Documentation	The documentation has been used to solve problems derived from the nextcloud configuration and its connection with the deployment.
User Support	User support contacted: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Short duration of one week for the nextcloud tokens • Disk space problems

Table EA2.1: Summary of the AI4EOSC integrated components used in the DigitalAlimenta use case.

Achieved results

After carrying out several experiments to find the optimal hyperparameters and reduce overfitting, we have managed to train a model to predict the weight of apples, focusing on three varieties: Fuji, Golden and Granny Smith. The results obtained during the bootstrap with 100 samples of 1000 images each are presented in [Table EA2.2](#) showing the Mean Absolute Error (MAE) of the model and the 95% confidence interval for the custom dataset. :

Metric	Result		Dataset
Mean Absolute Error (g)	27.38 g		Custom
95% confidence interval	26.47 g	28.29 g	

Table EA2.2: Mean Absolute Error of the model developed and 95% confidence interval for the custom dataset.

Figure EA2.1 shows a concrete example of one of the images with a fruit whose weight is to be predicted with the developed model, as well as the saliency maps to analyse the parts of the image that the model is focusing on when making the predictions.

Figure EA2.1: Example of the saliency maps obtained for a single image prediction.

Planned improvements

In future updates, we plan to conduct additional tests on this model with the aim of improving it further, if possible. In addition, we intend to develop new models for the rest of the target fruits of the project, which include pears, oranges and bananas. In order to do so, the use of a computing environment with the appropriate requirements is fundamental (specially in terms of GPUs and CPU cores). Finally, it will be necessary to create an API that will give users the possibility to make predictions and obtain accurate measurements for their dietary studies. This step will allow a smoother and more accessible integration of the tool into the food research environment.

4. - PLATFORM FEEDBACK

Following the Agile methodology, it is important for the development and continuous improvement of the project to foster customer collaboration and understand better the feedback of users about the platform. The direct communication with users is supported via bi-weekly meetings, where also user feedback is continuously monitored. In addition, we conducted a survey with the following questions:

- What platform components do you already use?
- What platform components do you plan to use?
- What do you find GOOD about the platform?
- What do you find DIFFICULT on the platform?
- What do you find MISSING on the platform?

The results are summarised in [Figure FE.1](#), [Figure FE.2](#), and [Table FE.1](#).

Figure FE.1: Current usage of the platform components.

What platform components do you plan to use?

6 responses

Figure FE.2: Planned usage of the platform components.

Good	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Offer of reach computing resources (CPU, GPU, RAM), storage ● Documentation, tutorials, and user support ● User-friendly marketplace ● Container-based approach for reproducibility ● Integration of new services (e.g. MLflow, OSCAR) ● Development environments like Jupyterlab or VSCode
Difficult	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● A bit non-intuitive: a lots of services, sites & options, difficult to get started ● Resource restrictions (e.g. limited GPU size, memory, disk space) ● Deployments may disappear or be reset ● Not easy to debug on large datasets
Missing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Image annotation tools ● More computing resources and storage ● Easy way to share the development environment with team members ● Simple default GUI for modules ● Tools to visualise training metrics ● Data management tool ● More video tutorials and demos

Table FE.1: User feedback on the AI4EOSC Platform.

As the survey shows, the use cases are focused now more on the components targeting the development of AI models rather than serving AI modules in production. Tools and services for the inference provision like OSCAR, AI4Compose, or monitoring of AI models in-production as Drift detection, more complex training approaches such as Federated learning, or Infrastructure Manager for deployment of complex infrastructures are expected to be used in the second half of the project. Also, MLflow usage is going to increase, given that the service became available to the users on M13 (September 2023).

[Table FE.1](#) summarises the user’s feedback in the text form and suggests where the platform can be improved. This information is especially important for the developers and providers, as well as for next updates and releases of the platform. Some of the issues mentioned among difficult and missing items are already being addressed, others have been taken into account. The list below highlights ongoing and planned actions:

- The online documentation is being continuously improved.
- New tutorials and demos are in preparation. This in addition will be supported by a series of webinars planned for engaging new users (see next Sec. 5).
- New computing resources are being added to the platform, including new cloud providers.
- The platform was undergoing active development, where some instabilities were present. The first release of the platform on M18 (February 2024) is expected to solve most of them.
- Image annotation tools are going to be added, the first one is CVAT⁴⁰
- Sharing of deployments coincides with the experiment-centric approach being investigated in WP5 “Experiment-centric AI services”.
- A GUI interface based on the Gradio⁴¹ tool is planned to be added to the DEEPaaS API Python package [[deepaas](#)].

5. - ENGAGING EXTERNAL USERS

The first release of the AI4EOSC platform is scheduled for M18 (end of February 2024) (see [Figure 3.1](#)). Right after that, the dissemination activities to onboard external user communities will start. The activity will be done in close coordination with WP2, “Project impact and cross-project collaboration”, and include:

- dissemination via EOSC channels
- organising a series of dedicated webinars
- presenting platform at relevant conferences
- collocation of workshops and tutorials at the conferences
- contacting scientific communities directly
- organising an online course to facilitate the onboarding of new users

The preparation with WP2 has already started, and e.g. the topics for the webinars are defined and speakers are prescribed.

⁴⁰ <https://github.com/opencv/cvat>

⁴¹ <https://www.gradio.app/>

6. - CONCLUSION

The AI4EOSC project progresses in establishing the AI platform and the AI4OS software stack to deliver an enhanced set of services for the development and serving of AI/ML/DL models and applications for EOSC. Three use cases act in different scientific domains. They steer the development of the platform and move forward in implementing the platform solutions. These solutions aim to cover the whole AI/ML/DL development cycle and include serving AI models and monitoring in production. This deliverable describes the platform solutions from the point-of-view of users as it is available at the moment. We furthermore present the status of the use cases, their achieved results, integrated components, and plans for the second half of the project. All use cases of the project delivered minimum viable products and are advancing towards more featured solutions. Also, two early adopters from external communities described their progress and the usage of the platform. The leading-by-example approach delivered two general-purpose AI modules and showed planned improvements. Finally, the feedback collected from all use cases was analysed together with ongoing and planned activities to enhance the platform. At the current phase of the project, use cases concentrate on development, which is reflected in what platform components are used. Taking advantage of more components and AI advanced techniques is expected in the second part of the project. After the first release of the platform, engaging external research communities is envisaged, and corresponding plans are presented.

REFERENCES

[**ai4eosc**] AI4EOSC (2024), <https://ai4eosc.eu/> . [Accessed 12-01-2024].

[**egi-check-in**] EGI Check-in: a proxy service to connect federated Identity Providers, <https://docs.egi.eu/users/aai/check-in/>, [Accessed on 06.02.2024]

[**cookiecutter**] Cookiecutter: Better Project Templates, <https://cookiecutter.readthedocs.io/> , [Accessed on 06.02.2024]

[**deepaas**] Lopez Garcia, A. "DEEPaaS API: a REST API for Machine Learning and Deep Learning models". In: Journal of Open Source Software 4(42) (2019), pp. 1517. ISSN: 2475-9066. DOI: [10.21105/joss.01517](https://doi.org/10.21105/joss.01517) .
GitHub repository: <https://github.com/ai4os/deepaas>

[**MLflow**] MLflow: A Machine Learning Lifecycle Platform, <https://github.com/mlflow/mlflow/>, [Accessed on 04.01.2024]

[**TF-Federated**] TF-Federated. 2024. Tensorflow Federated: Machine Learning on Decentralized Data. <https://www.tensorflow.org/federated> [Accessed 09-01-2024]

[PySyft] OpenMined. 2024. OpenMined/PySyft. <https://github.com/OpenMined/PySyft> [Accessed 09-01-2024]

[rcnn] R. Girshick, J. Donahue, T. Darrell and J. Malik, "Rich Feature Hierarchies for Accurate Object Detection and Semantic Segmentation," 2014 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition, Columbus, OH, USA, 2014, pp. 580-587, doi: 10.1109/CVPR.2014.81.

[fast-rcnn] R. Girshick, "Fast R-CNN," 2015 IEEE International Conference on Computer Vision (ICCV), Santiago, Chile, 2015, pp. 1440-1448, doi: 10.1109/ICCV.2015.169

[frcnn] Ren, S.; He, K.; Girshick, R.; Sun, J. Faster R-CNN: Towards Real-Time Object Detection with Region Proposal Networks. IEEE Trans. Pattern Anal. Mach. Intell. 2017, 39, 1137–1149.

[yolo] J. Redmon, S. Divvala, R. Girshick and A. Farhadi, "You Only Look Once: Unified, Real-Time Object Detection," in 2016 IEEE Conference on Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (CVPR), Las Vegas, NV, USA, 2016 pp. 779-788. doi: 10.1109/CVPR.2016.91

[yolov8] Reis, D., Kupec, J., Hong, J., & Daoudi, A. (2023). Real-Time Flying Object Detection with YOLOv8. arXiv preprint arXiv:2305.09972.

[ultralytics_yolov8] Jocher, G., Chaurasia, A., & Qiu, J. (2023). YOLO by Ultralytics (Version 8.0.0) [Computer software]. <https://github.com/ultralytics/ultralytics>

[ultralytics] <https://github.com/ultralytics>

[FATE] FATE. 2024. FATE (Federated AI Technology Enabler). <https://github.com/FederatedAI/FATE> [Accessed 09-01-2024]

[flower] Daniel J Beutel, Taner Topal, Akhil Mathur, Xinchu Qiu, Javier Fernandez-Marques, Yan Gao, Lorenzo Sani, Hei Li Kwing, Titouan Parcollet, Pedro PB de Gusmão, and Nicholas D Lane. 2020. Flower: A Friendly Federated Learning Research Framework. arXiv preprint arXiv:2007.14390 (2020).

[nvflare] Holger R Roth, Yan Cheng, Yuhong Wen, Isaac Yang, Ziyue Xu, Yuan-Ting Hsieh, Kristopher Kersten, Ahmed Harouni, Can Zhao, Kevin Lu, et al. 2022. Nvidia flare: Federated learning from simulation to real-world. arXiv preprint <https://arxiv.org/abs/2210.13291> (2022)

[FL] Syreen Banabilah, Moayad Aloqaily, Eitaa Alsayed, Nida Malik, and Yaser Jararweh. 2022. Federated learning review: Fundamentals, enabling technologies, and future applications. Information processing & management 59, 6 (2022), 103061

[AI4OSdocs] AI4OS documentation. <https://docs.ai4os.eu/en/latest/>. Accessed on 26-01-2024.

[Cespedes2022] Sisniega, Jaime Céspedes, and Álvaro López García. "Frouros: A Python library for drift detection in Machine Learning problems." arXiv preprint arXiv:2208.06868 (2022), <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2208.06868>

[udocker] J. Gomes et al., Enabling rootless Linux Containers in multi-user environments: The udocker tool, Computer Physics Communications, 2018, ISSN 0010-4655, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cpc.2018.05.021>

GitHub repository: <https://github.com/indigo-dc/udocker>

[seg-anything] Kirillov, A., Mintun, E., Ravi, N., Mao, H., Rolland, C., Gustafson, L., Xiao, T., Whitehead, S., Berg, A. C., Lo, W.-Y., Dollár, P., & Girshick, R. (2023). Segment Anything. arXiv preprint arXiv:2304.02643.

[zero-shot] Xian, Y., Lampert, H. C., Schiele, B., & Akata, Z. (2018). Zero-Shot Learning - A Comprehensive Evaluation of the Good, the Bad and the Ugly. IEEE Transactions on Pattern Analysis and Machine Intelligence (TPAMI).

[RNA] Taubert, O., von der Lehr, F., Bazarova, A. et al. RNA contact prediction by data efficient deep learning. *Commun Biol* 6, 913 (2023). <https://doi.org/10.1038/s42003-023-05244-9>

[DigitalAlimenta] DigitalAlimenta (2024), <https://digitalalimenta.csic.es/>. [Accessed 13-01-2024].

[GPT] Radford, A., & Narasimhan, K. (2018). Improving Language Understanding by Generative Pre-Training.

[BERT] Devlin, J., Chang, M. W., Lee, K., & Toutanova, K. (2019). BERT: Pre-training of Deep Bidirectional Transformers for Language Understanding. *arXiv preprint arXiv:1810.04805*

[iMagine-D3.2] Alibabaei, K., Kozlov, V. (2024). iMagine D3.2 Technical development roadmap for the AI image analysis use cases (update) (1 Under EC Review). Zenodo. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10619470>

